

AN EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION INTO THE USE OF INSERTS TO ENHANCE THE STATIC PERFORMANCE OF THIN COMPOSITE BOLTED LAP JOINTS

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SUMMARY: The aim of this program was to investigate the use of interference fit and bonded inserts in thin 8 ply quasi-isotropic, composite mechanically fastened single lap joints. The static behaviour of the joint was evaluated with various insert configurations. Bearing tests were also undertaken in order to evaluate the bearing behaviour of the laminate with the various insert configurations. Results from the bearing tests showed slight improvement in the bearing strength for press-fit straight inserts. A significant increase, up to 100%, in bearing strength was observed for the bonded top-hat insert compared to the no inserts case. The failure mode for the bolted joint specimens, without the inserts, appeared to be predominantly pull through of the fastener, even though the specimens were designed to fail in bearing. The pull-through type failure was caused by the secondary bending in the specimen which resulted in high severe pull-through stresses by the fastener head and collar. The top-hat inserts assisted in reducing the high pull-through stress exerted by the fastener head and collar and in some cases was so successful that the failure mode changed from pull-through to bearing with a corresponding 30% increase in the load carrying capacity of the joint.

KEYWORDS: inserts, bolted composite joints, g/e bolted joints.

INTRODUCTION

Lightweight, efficient, thin skinned composite laminates are experiencing increasing use in aerospace structures. In most applications thin laminates are bonded together, however mechanically fastened joints are also used extensively because of the requirements for inspection, manufacturing breaks, assembly and equipment access, and replacement/repair of damaged structures. However the strength of composite laminates are considerably weakened by the presence of fastener holes. For composites the maximum strength efficiency, ie [bolt joint strength] / [un-notched strength], of a single bolted joint in tension is only about 40% compared to 65% for metals. This is mainly due to the high stress concentrations, K_t from the high degree of brittleness, or lack of plasticity, and high degree of anisotropy of the material. In metallic structures yielding acts to relieve local high stresses and also to equalise uneven load distribution. Therefore a technique which will allow a more compliant response around a composite hole, in order to relieve stress concentrations, should result in an increase in composite bolted joint strength (ie promotes fastener load sharing.)

There are a variety of techniques available to increase the strength of mechanically fastened joints in composites. These include:

1. Softening around the hole to reduce the stress concentration at the hole by:
 - (a) installing softening strips, ie substituting 0° carbon fibres by strips of glass fibres about four diameters wide around the hole or
 - (b) incorporating additional $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.
2. Increasing the stiffness around the hole by introducing extra 0° fibres or by incorporating a thin titanium alloy sheet in the laminate around the hole. The latter is quite effective in increasing the bearing strength of the hole.
3. Bonding doublers over the hole.
4. Installing bonded inserts to reduce the stress concentration as well as increasing the bearing strength of the laminate. Inserts can be used to repair damaged bolted joints and are used to restore the bearing strength of the laminate.

Hart-Smith [1] postulates that, as long as no fibres are broken when the bolts are installed, interference-fit fasteners should cause a much larger softened area due to the development of a delamination zone which will provide stress concentration relief. However, forcing fasteners into composite holes to produce an interference-fit may cause undesirable/excessive matrix, fibre and delamination damage around the hole. However controlled expansion of a sleeve that remains statically in contact with the fibres, while a fastener is pressed in, can produce interferences of up to 0.178 mm.

In general the benefits of interference-fit fasteners are to [2] [3]

- i) reduce fastener rotation, which is more severe for thick composite laminates
- ii) lower joint deflection
- iii) reduced overall backlash,
- iv) equal fastener load sharing,
- v) reduction in relative fastener flexibility,
- vi) delayed or reduced hole elongation, especially in fatigue,
- vi) reduce water intrusion/reduce fuel leakage problems and
- vii) improve electrical conductivity and lightning strike protection,

Interference-fit fasteners show only slight improvements in initial static strength, however there is substantial evidence that interference (close-fits) will substantially improve the fatigue life of composite bolted joints. The life of composite joints with loose fitting holes is compromised, especially for reversed loading fatigue (i.e. compression-tension), due to back and forth rocking of the fastener. Unlike metallic structures, large interferences are of no real benefit in composite bolted joints since all that is desired is a "net" fit. However, a net fit is not practical therefore the interference limit need only be the accumulation of the tolerances with the net fit being the minimum [2].

The aim of this study [4] was to improve the static strength of thin composite mechanically fastened single lap joints by incorporating metallic inserts.

Three types of fasteners, viz. rivet, a swagged collar fastener and an interference fastener system were also evaluated, without the inclusion of the aluminium or steel inserts. The experimental study involved subjecting the specimens to increasing uniaxial load until the specimen failed. Strain measurements and high speed video images, obtained during the test, indicated the degree of secondary bending occurring in the specimen. Tests were also undertaken in order to evaluate the bearing behaviour of the laminate with the various insert configurations.

SPECIMEN

Lap Joint Specimens

Coupons

The material used in this experimental investigation was AS4/3501-6 carbon fibre/epoxy resin system. The 130 mm by 38 mm coupons were cut from 900 mm by 600 mm panels of layup $[\pm 45, 0, 90]_s$ and $[\pm 45, 90, 0]_s$, the long dimension being aligned parallel to the 0° fibres. In order to verify that there were no manufacturing defects, the panels were ultrasonically inspected before cutting

The specimens have been designed to fail in bearing only, hence the width-to-diameter (w/d) and edge distance-to-diameter (e/d) ratios varied between 5.7 - 9.2 and 2.8 - 4.6. Fig. 1a shows the tandem fastener lap-joint specimen used in this investigation. The joint manufacturing process were conducted in accordance with McDonnell Douglas process specifications [5].

Fig. 1: (a) Tandem fastener single lap-joint specimen used in this investigation.
(b) Configurations of either press-fit or bonded aluminium and steel inserts.

Fasteners

The three types of fasteners evaluated were (1) NAS 1919M05 rivets, (2) NAS 2015 pin & NAS 2013 - 05 collar, and (3) CIL9SP-VC05-02 sleeved pin and CIFIC-MV05 collar. These types of fasteners have different fits, standard, close, and interference. They were the same type of fasteners used by Au-Yeung et al [6]. Fasteners were installed at HdH Victoria, using standard aerospace procedures. The fastener diameters were those recommended by the manufacturer for this particular laminate thickness. A fourth fastener, similar to type (2) was also evaluated. It comprised of a NAS2013-08 collar and NAS 2018H05 fasteners which had the same diameter as the outside diameter of the inserts, ie. 6.35mm.

Inserts

Three basic insert types were considered in this study, viz., (a) straight insert, (b) hat shaped inserts and (c) hat inserts with tapered top, these are depicted in Fig. 1b. The inserts were made from two different types of materials, aluminium or mild steel in order to study the effects of different insert compliances.

The inserts were installed with either a slight interference (press) fit or bonded into the hole. The interference-fit inserts were pressed into a hole of 6.35 mm nominal diameter, the level of interference was nominally 40 μm . The bonding installation procedure used an acrylic adhesive, Versilock 201/17, a room temperature curing adhesive which requires approximately 24 hours to cure. The adhesive thickness was allowed for in the design of the inserts which had "top-hats", a section of the bond line is depicted in Fig 1a. The bond thickness was set to approximately 0.18 mm, this was taken from experience gained at AMRL

in bonding inserts in metallic components [7]. Therefore in this case the nominal hole size for a 6.35 mm diameter insert was 6.71 mm.

Initially the jig used to install the inserts in the coupons only allowed one insert at any time to be installed. Whilst this technique has been used in other testing programs at AMRL with inserts in thick aluminium bolted joints it was unsuccessful in this testing program. The inaccurate tolerance of the concentricity of the insert in the coupon lead to inaccurate hole spacing, causing problems during the fastener installation stage. Consequently, a new more rigid jig which was designed to a tighter tolerance was manufactured. The new jig allowed the coupons to be clamped along their length enabling two inserts at a time to be installed, hence achieving the correct hole spacing. Nominally three specimens of each type were manufactured and tested.

After assembly the specimens were ultrasonically C-scanned and inspected for any manufacturing / assembly damage around the hole

A limited number of specimens were strain gauged in order to determine bending and in-plane strains during testing. Strain gauge locations are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: (a) Strain gauge locations on (b) Deformed shape of two fastener single lap joint specimen.

Bearing Specimens

Two basic pin diameters were used, viz., 4.2 and 6.35 mm. The 4.2 mm diameter pin was used to load the coupons with no inserts, with interference-fit and bonded inserts. The 6.35 mm diameter pin was used to load a coupon with no inserts. The specimen and fixture used to undertake the bearing test is shown in Fig. 3a and 3b. This allowed the bearing specimen to be subjected to tensile or compressive loads.

TEST PROCEDURE

Lap Joint Tests

Mechanically fastened joint specimens were placed, with spacers, in the MTS 100 kN uniaxial testing machine as shown in Fig . 4. (The strain gauged specimens were subjected to an initial tensile ramp load up to approximately 2 kN, to ensure that the experimental set-up was correct and to check strain gauge readings). The specimens were then subjected to increasing uniaxial tensile load until failure occurred. In all cases the loading rate was 2 kN/min.

The strains, loads and displacements were acquired using a PC-based data acquisition systems. Data manipulation was undertaken after testing to determine in-plane and bending strains. Some of the tests undertaken were observed using a high speed video system.

Fig. 3: (a) Typical bearing test specimen. (b) Bearing test arrangement. (c) Load vs deflection of a typical bearing test.

Fig. 4: (a) Specimens, with spacers, in the MTS 100 kN uni-axial testing machine. (b) Specimen mounted in hydraulic grips of servo hydraulic testing machine.

Bearing Tests

The bearing test arrangement is depicted in Fig. 3b and shows the location of a 25 mm gauge clip gauge positioned between points A and B. This allowed specimen deflection to be measured whilst the specimen was being loaded. Load and clip gauge readings were recorded while the specimens were tested to failure. All tests were performed at room temperature.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Fasteners

The results of the ultimate load test of the lap joint specimen with the various fastener types and without the inclusion of the aluminium or steel inserts are presented in Fig. 5a. Pull through of the fasteners was the failure mode in these specimens, as illustrated in Fig. 5b.

The interference fit specimens had the highest ultimate load, this was expected since the K_t decreases with reduction in the hole clearance. (ie bolt diameter increases). When a uniaxial load is applied to a plate containing a hole or a hole containing an unloaded fastener with a large radial clearance the hole will ovalise, in the direction of the applied load, causing a stress concentration at the side of the hole. Ovalisation of the hole can be restricted by reducing the radial clearance between the hole and the fastener, thus reducing the stress concentration. If interference is introduced the stress concentration is reduced further due to load transfer by friction from the plate to the fastener. It is postulated [8], that the introduction of interference-fit fasteners in composites could contribute to an increase in static strength.

The introduction of slight countersinks caused a slight decrease in the joint strength. The countersink was introduced to reduce the assembly damage between the edge of the fastener hole and the nominal radius under the head of the fasteners.

Of the two different layups ($[\pm 45, 0, 90]_s$ and $[\pm 45, 90, 0]_s$) the latter gave slightly lower results. The NAS2015 pin & NAS2013-05 had less scatter in the results.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: (a) Comparison of ultimate load for the three types of fasteners in a single lap joint arrangement. (b) Typical example of pull-through failure.

Bearing Tests

Load vs deflection of a typical bearing test is depicted in Fig. 3c. Initially there is “bedding in” of the pin followed by a linear region. The load where the deflection becomes non-linear indicates the initial failure load, and this point is defined as the bearing yield point. The maximum load carried by the hole was defined as the ultimate bearing load. The yield and ultimate bearing loads for each configuration are depicted in Fig. 6a and 6b.

The results show that the bonded tapered hat insert gave the highest bearing yield and ultimate loads. The interference tapered hat insert gave the lowest bearing yield and ultimate loads, due to the insert tilted out of the hole. This did not occur for the bonded case. The tilt of the inserts was caused by a localised bending moment. The length of bearing surface in the insert is twice as long as the bearing surface on the outside of the tapered hat insert, these two surface are eccentric to each other which produces a localised moment.

Fig. 6: (a) Yield and (b) ultimate bearing loads for various hole diameters and insert configurations .

The 6.35 mm pin and the interference fit straight steel insert case had similar bearing yield loads. The bearing yield load for the aluminium interference fit insert was nominally 33% to 50% higher than the steel insert and no insert case. The 6.35 mm pin used in the no insert case was made from the same material as the steel inserts. The aluminium has a similar stiffness as the composite material, whereas the stiffness of the steel is considerably higher than the composite, and would cause a higher bearing stress concentration than the aluminium. However the bonded aluminium tapered hat insert had the highest bearing yield load, thus it was expected that the aluminium tapered hat insert in a single lap joint would give the best performance.

Lap joint tests

The results of the lap joint test are presented in Fig. 7. All the lap joints failed by pull through of the fastener head or collar, see Fig. 5b. with the exception of the bonded double hat inserts. Some of the fasteners failed in tension because the grip length was too short, i.e. the collars were pulled away. The bonded tapered hat inserts failed in bearing, whereas the bonded hat inserts failed in a combination of net tension and bearing. The failure modes are depicted in Fig. 8. The high speed video images obtained during the testing showed the fasteners “rocking” and digging into the composite material until it eventually pulled through. To quantify the secondary bending in these joints strain gauges were attached.

The in-plane and bending strains for the 6.35 mm diameter fastener are plotted in Fig. 9a and 9b respectively. Fig. 10a and 10b shows the bending strains for gauges 7 and 8 and 1 and 2 respectively. The strain gauges 7 and 8 are located on opposite faces between the two fasteners near the edge of the specimen, see Fig. 3. Similarly strain gauges 1 and 2 are the far field gauges on opposite faces located near the testing machine hydraulic grips. The results show in-plane strain between the two fasteners (gauges 7 and 8) are approximately half that of the far field gauges 1 and 2. Strain gauges 7 and 8 have more bending than the far field gauges 1 and 2 and at approximately 6 kN there was a sudden reduction in bending, the total in-plane load showed a slight drop off in load. The sudden reduction occurred with the similar type but smaller fastener (NAS2015). The other two fasteners NAS1919 rivets and CIL9SP interference rivet showed less secondary bending. The bonded tapered insert showed large secondary bending between the two fasteners as well as in the far field.

(a) (b)
 Fig. 7: Ultimate test of (a) single and (b) double inserts in lap joints with NAS2015 pins & NAS2013-05 collars.

(a) (b) (c)
 Fig. 8: Failure modes of bonded inserts: (a) Bonded tapered hat insert showing bearing failure. (b) Bonded hat insert with net-tension failure mode. (c) Bonded hat insert with combined pull-through, net-tension and bearing type failure.

(a) (b)
 Fig. 9: The (a) in-plane and (b) bending strains for the 6.35mm diameter fastener NAS2018.

Fig. 10: A comparison of bending strains for gauges (a) 1 and 2 and (b) 7 and 8 for various fasteners / insert combinations.

Installing inserts generally means the overall diameter of the fastener has increased resulting in a reduction of the bearing stress for a given load and consequently an increase in joint strength. The inserts had the same outside diameter as the 6.35mm diameter fastener and the performance of the various insert / fastener configurations are also compared with the large diameter fastener. This can be seen in the bearing test results depicted in Fig. 6, where there is no bending, however if bending is present the insert may degrade the performance.

The mechanism which caused these joints to fail is due to the localised secondary bending, which causes the fasteners to rotate/rock, causing the fastener to pull through the composite material. This mechanism was clearly displayed in the high speed video images.

The bonded tapered hat insert increases the distance between the center line of the fastener and the reacting force between the insert and the composite material, since the localised moment remains constant, it implies that the reactive force must decrease. The reactive force is higher the closer to the center-line of the fastener, this force produced localised highly stressed region which eventually crushes/damages in the composite material and allows the fastener to rotate /rock. As the load is increased the fastener continues to bite into the composite material until the fastener pulls through.

The reactive force is lower for the bonded tapered hat insert, also there is a greater area which reduces the stresses at the edge of the insert and it does not damage the composite material. The bending moment between the two fasteners is it reduced with the tapered hat insert in comparison with the 6.35mm fastener, however it induces a greater far field bending.

Two of the three bonded aluminium tapered hat double insert lap joint specimens performed slightly better than the 6.35mm fasteners see Fig. 7b. The third specimen which was strain gauged, the result of which are presented in Fig 10 failed below 12kN

The bearing test showed that the bonded aluminium tapered hat insert gave the best performance, where as the interference fit aluminium tapered hat insert also rotated causing premature failure by fastener pull-through. A similar mechanism occurred for the interference fit tapered insert in the lap joint specimens.

Rocking/rotating of the fasteners appears to be restricted by bonding the tapered hat insert causing a change in failure mode to bearing and a corresponding increase in failure load. The load is similar to the 6.35mm diameter fastener which has a higher clamping force than the tapered hat insert. The 6.35mm diameter fastener single lap joint specimen failed in pull through mode, where as the tapered hat insert failed in bearing. The aluminium tapered hat arrangement is approximately 30% lighter than the 6.35mm diameter fastener.

Other factors which would have assisted the bonded tapered insert is the ability to transfer load through shear in the adhesive, under the hat, this enabling an additional load path besides bearing of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

Results from the bearing tests showed slight improvement in the bearing strength for press-fit straight inserts. A significant increase, up to 100%, in bearing strength was observed for the bonded top-hat insert compared to the no insert case. The failure mode for the bolted joint specimens, without the inserts, appeared to be predominantly pull through of the fastener, even though the specimens were designed to fail in bearing. The pull-through type failure was caused by the secondary bending in the specimen which resulted in high shear pull-through stresses by the fastener head and collar. The top-hat inserts assisted in reducing the high pull-through stress exerted by the fastener head and collar and in some cases was so successful that the failure mode changed from pull-through to bearing with a corresponding 30% increase in the load carrying capacity of the joint.

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